

Supplement to: SOP “Image curation and publication”

This supplemental material can be used to conduct the image curation and publication steps described in the SOP document “Image curation and publication”. Feel free to adjust to your specific needs! All material in this supplement is released under CC-0.

Content:

- A template folder structure to organize image data and metadata
- A task list to document the execution of the “Image curation and publication” SOP
- An image acquisition protocol sheet to fill in prior / during image acquisition
- Data management plan (DMP) sections for image data

References:

- SOP “Image curation and publication”: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5704846>
- SOP “iFDO creation”: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5681429>
- SOP „iFDO creation“ supplement: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5683081>
- FAIR marine images: <https://marine-imaging.com/fair>

Information about this document:

Title: SOP „Image curation and publication“ supplement

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Abstract: This supplemental material can be used to conduct the image curation and publication steps described in the SOP document “Image curation and publication”. That SOP describes how research image data like photos and videos can be published for scientific use.

Note: This material is kept generic. Adjust it to your needs and include specific information on your infrastructure to adapt it to your institute / workflow.

DOI:

Keywords: Image, curation, publication, photo, video, iFDO

License: CC-0

Related Identifiers:

Communities: MareHub of the Helmholtz Association

Revisions:

Version	Date	Author	Comment
v1.0.0	2021/11	Timm Schoening	Initial draft of a public text version of this SOP. Compiled from discussions in the MareHub AG Videos/Images.

Folder structure to organize image data and image metadata

How to structure data on disk should not be enforced by any SOP. However, we recommend the following structure to aid the automation of data curation and publication workflows. It is based on several best-practices guides for handling research data (e.g. <https://github.com/drivendata/cookiecutter-data-science>). Using this template structure allows you to utilize the full potential of the MarIQT python software for image data curation.

Overall, data is stored in one or many *base-paths*, given in the example below as `/<volume>/<project>`.

The base-path is likely to be a network drive provided by a research vessel, a research group or technical team. Some disciplines/groups like to split their data by sensor first. This is not recommended but certainly possible. In that case, the paths would look like this:

image-project	
image-event	
image-set-name	
image-platform	
image-sensor	
image-creators	

Done	Who	When	What
Preparation phase			
	Scientists	Before project start	Create Data Management Plan (DMP) in cloud
	Scientists	Before image acquisition	Collect project information
Acquisition phase			
	Scientists	Before image acquisition	Begin an acquisition protocol
	Scientists	Image acquisition	Acquire images
	Scientists	Image acquisition	Acquire navigation data
	Scientists	After image acquisition	Complete the acquisition protocol
	Scientists	Before image curation	Structure the data on disk
	Scientists	Before image curation	Split files in size or to subfolders
	Scientists	After image acquisition	Curate image data
	Scientists	After image acquisition	Curate navigation data
	Scientists	After data curation	Create iFDOs for metadata
	Scientists	After iFDO creation	Create Data Processing Report (DPR)
	Scientists	After data processing report	Update Data Management Plan (DMP)
Publication phase			
	Scientists	After iFDO creation	Publish iFDOs
	Scientists	After iFDO publication	Publish navigation data through web interfaces
	Scientists	After workspace creation	Migrate image data to web server
	RDM team	After image migration	Make data available for annotation (optional)
	Scientists	After image migration	Publish data in PANGAEA (optional)
	RDM team	After publication	Update Data Management Plan (DMP)

Note: Lines in green are recommended steps that make your image curation and publication life easier.

image-project	_____	image-event	_____
image-set-name	_____	image-creators	_____
image-platform	_____	image-sensor	_____
Date	_____	Latitude / Longitude	_____

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Focus is set to: _____ | <input type="checkbox"/> F-Number is set to: _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Objective lens is cleaned | <input type="checkbox"/> Dummy plugs are connected |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Camera is set to UTC time | <input type="checkbox"/> Recorder is set to UTC time |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Cool / dry air is inside pressure housing | <input type="checkbox"/> All seals are greased |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Power cable is connected | <input type="checkbox"/> Data cable is connected |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Platform origin x-offset: _____ cm | (Forward is positive) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Platform origin y-offset: _____ cm | (Right is positive) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Platform origin z-offset: _____ cm | (Down is positive) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Camera view angle: _____ ° | (0° is horizontal, 90° is vertical down, -90° is up) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Laser reference is aligned | <input type="checkbox"/> Laser reference distance: _____ cm |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Protective covers are taken off | <input type="checkbox"/> Glass port is cleaned |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Storage space on recorder: _____ GB | <input type="checkbox"/> Photos of setup with scale reference taken |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sample images on deck have been taken | <input type="checkbox"/> Calibration images on deck have been taken |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Switch on platform: _____ date/time | <input type="checkbox"/> Switch on camera: _____ date/time |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Switch on lights | <input type="checkbox"/> Auxiliary sensors (e.g. CTD) are recording |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Underwater navigation is ready, Beacon ID: _____ | <input type="checkbox"/> Underwater navigation data is recording |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Start recording images: _____ date/time | <input type="checkbox"/> Start streaming images to network (e.g. VNC) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Annotation protocol is prepared | <input type="checkbox"/> Start annotation |

Comments:

image-acquisition: <input type="checkbox"/> photo <input type="checkbox"/> video <input type="checkbox"/> slide
image-quality: <input type="checkbox"/> raw <input type="checkbox"/> processed <input type="checkbox"/> product
image-deployment: <input type="checkbox"/> mapping <input type="checkbox"/> stationary <input type="checkbox"/> survey <input type="checkbox"/> exploration <input type="checkbox"/> experiment <input type="checkbox"/> sampling
image-navigation: <input type="checkbox"/> satellite <input type="checkbox"/> beacon <input type="checkbox"/> transponder <input type="checkbox"/> reconstructed
image-scale-reference: <input type="checkbox"/> 3D camera <input type="checkbox"/> calibrated camera <input type="checkbox"/> laser marker <input type="checkbox"/> optical flow
image-illumination: <input type="checkbox"/> sunlight <input type="checkbox"/> artificial light <input type="checkbox"/> mixed light
image-resolution: <input type="checkbox"/> km <input type="checkbox"/> hm <input type="checkbox"/> dam <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> cm <input type="checkbox"/> mm <input type="checkbox"/> μm
image-marine-zone: <input type="checkbox"/> seafloor <input type="checkbox"/> water column <input type="checkbox"/> sea surface <input type="checkbox"/> atmosphere <input type="checkbox"/> laboratory
image-spectral-resolution: <input type="checkbox"/> grayscale <input type="checkbox"/> rgb <input type="checkbox"/> multi-spectral <input type="checkbox"/> hyper-spectral
image-capture-mode: <input type="checkbox"/> timer <input type="checkbox"/> manual <input type="checkbox"/> mixed
image-camera-housing-viewport: <input type="checkbox"/> flatport <input type="checkbox"/> domeport <input type="checkbox"/> other
image-time-synchronisation:
image-item-identification-scheme:
image-target-environment:
image-target-timescale:
image-spatial-constraints:
image-temporal-constraints:
image-objective:

Project information (add table to DMP once)

<Project name / ID>	
Summary of Project	<i>Description of the project scope and workplan.</i>
Location	<i>Geographic location of project (e.g. bounding box latitude / longitude)</i>
Start / End Date	<i>Beginning and end of the data creation and curation of the project</i>
Project Lead	<i>The one person that coordinates the entire project</i>
Data Representative	<i>One person that is responsible for the data during the project (Project Lead or designee).</i>
Collaborating Institutes	<i>List all partner institutes with lead representative</i>
Total data volume	<i>Estimation of the total data volume of new image sets and derived data products.</i>

(Project = Campaign = Experiment = Cruise)

New image sets to be acquired (repeat table in DMP for each image set)

Data that does not currently exist and will be collected or generated during the course of the project/campaign for the purpose of creating the final data products and/or project deliverables.

<Image set name>	
Data Representative	<i>This needs to be someone who has overall responsibility for image data acquisition, processing, quality control, documentation, and preservation. This could be the PI or a designee. (See General Project Information -> Data Representative)</i>
Description	<i>Is this a one-time image set, or an ongoing series of measurements? What is the actual or planned temporal coverage of the data? What is the actual or planned geographic coverage of the data?</i>
Collection Method	<i>E.g., ROV, AUV, OFOS, Drone, Lander, ...</i>
Data acquisition Standards	<i>Identify any standard protocols or methodologies that will be used to acquire the data, if available.</i>
Data Format & Type	<i>Identify the formats in which the data will be generated, maintained, and made available. E.g., JPEG, MOV, MPEG-4, TIFF, ...</i>
Licenses / Fees	<i>Will the project need to license any product to collect or process the data?</i>
Quality checks	<i>Identify the procedural steps for ensuring data quality of images</i>
Data Workflow	<i>Describe the data curation steps or provide an SOP reference</i>
Backup & Storage	<i>Describe the approach for backup and storage of the image data and metadata. How many copies will be maintained and how will they be synchronized? Are the data and backups going to be stored in multiple places and on different media types to protect against a single point of failure? Yes / No? If yes, please explain. Who will routinely check to ensure that backups are being done according to the backup plan you just described? Note: this needs to be someone closely associated with the actual storage and management of your project / campaign data.</i>
Volume Estimate	<i>How many MB, GB, TB, or PB</i>
Data Repository	<i>Identify repositories where you plan to share your data. Indicate if data will be integrated into an existing image set or offered as a new one. → Elements, PANGAEA</i>
Metadata (Schema)	<i>Identify the metadata standard that will be used to describe the data → iFDO</i>
Metadata URL	<i>A URL to the metadata schema → https://marine-imaging.com/fair/ifdos/iFDO-overview/</i>
Embargo	<i>If a request to limit access for a period of time after project completion is needed, please identify the length of the time and explain the reason for the extension.</i>
Access / Restrictions	<i>Identify any limitations on access or reuse (e.g., licenses, sensitive data, restricted data, software with license restrictions, etc.) and provide justification for restriction.</i>
File Name Convention	<i>Are file naming conventions going to be used that help describe the data? Yes / No?</i>
Data Lifespan	<i>Less than 5 years, 5–10 years, 10–20 years, 20–50 years, 50+ years</i>
Long-term data format	<i>Is the data format appropriate for long-term preservation (non-proprietary, machine-readable)? Yes / No? If not, please describe how you intend to convert.</i>
Additional Documents	<i>Which of the following will be included with your data? Supporting documents (i.e., fieldbooks), standardized logs, standard operating procedures etc..</i>
DOI	<i>To be added afterwards.</i>

Software (remove table if not needed and repeat table for each Software used)

<Software Name> <Software Version>	
Representative	<i>The person responsible for this software (project lead or lead developer)</i>
Description	<i>Provide a brief description of the software / code and its purpose.</i>
Source	<i>If the custom software or code can be accessed via an online repository, provide a link.</i>
License / Fees	<i>Identify any limitations on access or reuse.</i>
Maintenance / Support	<i>Describe the ongoing support and maintenance of the software tool after the project.</i>
Languages	<i>Identify the computing language / framework that was used.</i>
Environment	<i>Identify the operating system (e.g. Windows, Linux, MacOS)</i>

Derived Data Products (Repeat table for each Derived Data Product):

<Data Product Name>	
Data Representative	<i>The person responsible for collating this Data Product</i>
Description	<i>Describe the information that will be produced, including its characteristics, temporal scope and scale, and geographic scope and scale, when available.</i>
Data Format / Type	<i>Identify the formats in which the data will be generated, maintained, and made available. E.g., digital numeric, imagery, photographs, video, audio, database, tabular data etc. List format(s): e.g., ArcASCII, AVI, CSV, DOC, DOCX, GeoJSON, JPEG, JSON, MAT, MOV, MPEG-4, netCDF, PDF, SEGY, SHP, TIFF, TXT, XLS, XLSX, XML...</i>
Quality Checks	<i>Identify the procedural steps for ensuring data quality.</i>
Data Workflows	<i>Describe data processing steps or provide a scientific workflow to create the product.</i>
Backup & Storage	<i>Describe the approach for backup and storage of the information associated with the research project during the project. See Image set backup & storage for relevant aspects.</i>
Volume Estimate	<i>MB, GB, TB, or PB</i>
Data Repository	<i>Identify repositories where you plan to share your data.</i>
Metadata (Schema)	<i>Identify the metadata standard that will be used to describe the data.</i>
Metadata URL	<i>Please provide a URL to the metadata schema</i>
Non-existent Metadata	<i>If metadata are non-existent or non-compliant, please explain:</i>
Embargo	<i>If a request to limit access for a period of time after project completion is needed, please identify the length of the time and the reason for the extension.</i>
Access / Restrictions	<i>Identify any limitations on access or reuse (e.g., licenses, sensitive data, restricted data, software with license restrictions, etc.) and provide justification for restriction.</i>
Data Lifespan	<i>Less than 5 years, 5–10 years, 10–20 years, 20–50 years, 50+ years.</i>
Long-term data format	<i>Is the data format appropriate for long-term preservation (non-proprietary, machine-readable)? Yes / No? If not, please describe how you intend to convert.</i>
Additional documents	<i>Which of the following will be included? Supporting documents (i.e., fieldbooks), standardized logs, standard operating procedures etc..</i>
DM Resources	<i>Describe the proposal resources allocated for data management activities for the new data collected as a level of effort, total Euros allocated, or as a percentage of the total project's cost. Resources could include people's time or prop</i>
DOI	<i>To be added afterwards</i>